

How Ready Are Higher Education Students for E-learning? Insights from Jammu & Kashmir

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Abstract

In light of the rapid shift towards digital learning environments, assessing students' e-learning readiness is vital in developing countries, where unique infrastructural and socio-cultural challenges impact education. The study examines the e-learning readiness of 909 university students through the data collected using a self-developed "E-learning Readiness of Students" scale and analyzed with non-parametric techniques in SPSS V26. The results reveal that, majority of students have moderate level of readiness for e-learning. Contrary to expectations, gender, type of institution, and location had no significant impact on students' e-learning readiness. However, academic stream was a significant determinant, with students in Social Science showing higher readiness for e-learning compared to those in Science, Technology, Arts & Humanities, and other streams. Key differences were found in areas such as multitasking ability, software proficiency, online data retrieval, motivation for digital learning, and confidence in using e-learning tools. This study by highlighting the best and the least aspects of e-learning readiness calls for tailored digital education strategies to address the diverse needs of students. These findings provide valuable insights for policymakers and educators, particularly in relation to India's NEP 2020, which highlights the importance of digital learning. They offer a solid foundation for creating inclusive e-learning frameworks in higher education and play a key role in advancing successful e-learning implementation in India. Furthermore, they have global relevance, supporting the promotion of e-learning initiatives in similar institutions across developing countries.

Keywords: *E-learning, E-learning Readiness, Higher Education, Technological Readiness, Psychological Readiness, Infrastructure Readiness*

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Introduction

India's higher education system is critical for social and economic progress. As the world's second-largest, it's positioned to become a hub for quality education, driven by rising demand and increasing international students. According to the All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE), student enrollment reached 3.85 crore in 2019-2020, with 1,043 universities and over 42,000 colleges. In 2020-21, higher education institutions grew by 7.5% (MoE, 2021). However, rapid enrollment growth has led to issues like overcrowded classrooms and insufficient facilities, challenging institutions' ability to maintain quality standards (MoE, 2021; Yeravdekar et al., 2023). E-learning is considered a key solution to educational challenges in developing nations (UNESCO, 2006) and aligns with India's 2047 higher education vision (Yeravdekar et al., 2023). It offers flexibility, personalized learning, and high-quality multimedia content (Panda & Mishra, 2007). The NEP 2020 emphasizes technology integration for inclusive education (MHRD, 2020). Accordingly, the UGC has launched digital initiatives such as e-PG Pathshala, SWAYAM, NDL, DIKSHA, Shodhganga, virtual labs, and NPTEL to bolster India's e-learning ecosystem (MoE, 2021). Yet, a critical question persists: Are students ready to embrace these e-learning advancements and fully leverage digital education opportunities?

E-learning challenges in developing nations differ significantly from those in developed ones (Yawson & Yamoah, 2020). Research in these countries has largely focused on issues like technology access and contextual barriers, with less emphasis on individual readiness—an area commonly addressed in developed countries (Andersson & Grönlund, 2009; Ogbodoakum et al., 2022). Key obstacles include limited resources, poor infrastructure, and accessibility issues (Aung & Khaing, 2015). A primary reason for e-learning setbacks is often a lack of readiness to adopt digital systems (Wagiran et al., 2022). Additionally, emotional well-being and security concerns impact students' e-learning satisfaction (Estriegana et al., 2023). While extensive literature addresses ICT and e-learning in Indian higher education (Chawla & Joshi, 2012; Karanam et al., 2019; MHRD, 2020; Yeravdekar et al., 2023), understanding students' e-learning readiness in Jammu and Kashmir (J&K) remains underexplored. Most studies focus on particular states (Pingle, 2016; Vijaya Lakshmi et al., 2020) or specific disciplines (Chawla & Joshi, 2012), underscoring a need for targeted research in J&K. In Jammu and Kashmir (J&K), institutions like the University of Kashmir (UoK) and Central University of Kashmir (CUK) have introduced Learning Management Systems (LMS) and virtual labs. UoK's "E-Tutorials" platform (UoK, n.d.), and CUK's

digital content across subject offerings aim to enhance e-learning (CUK, n.d.), as do virtual labs in colleges in Anantnag and Jammu (Government College for Women, n.d.; Government Degree College Boys, Anantnag, 2021) underscoring the need to assess regional e-learning readiness (ELR). ELR measures an institution's "mental, physical, and structural preparedness for e-learning" (Borotis & Poulymenakou, 2004), including technological, organizational, and attitudinal readiness (Farazkish & Montazer, 2019). ELR also considers users' ability to navigate digital tools and adapt to online environments (Kaur & Abas, 2004). While technological readiness is well-explored, aspects like psychological and infrastructural readiness, as well as demographic impacts on students' ELR in J&K, require more research. This study's multidimensional ELR approach is crucial for guiding strategies that support quality e-learning alongside educational growth in India.

Objectives of the study

Our research targets four main objectives:

- (1) to evaluate students' level of e-learning readiness (ELR),
- (2) to identify the highest and lowest aspects of readiness,
- (3) to examine correlations between ELR dimensions, and
- (4) to investigate the influence of demographic characteristics on ELR.

Method and Procedure

We employed a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design, ideal for assessing each readiness dimension individually and analyzing interrelationships (McMillan & Schumacher, 2006). A nomothetic approach was adopted to focus on generalizable trends rather than individual differences. Data was gathered using an ELR of students scale with strong psychometric reliability.

Instrument and data collection

A review of the literature showed that e-learning readiness (ELR) dimensions vary widely across countries, often requiring a tailored approach. This underscored the need for a customized tool suited to our study's specific context. Drawing on several established self-assessment tools (Coopasami et al., 2017; Mahajan & Kalpana, 2018; Obi et al., 2018; Panda & Mishra, 2007; Pingle, 2016), the researchers developed a new "E-learning Readiness of Students" scale. This tool assessed Technological Readiness (TR), Psychological Readiness

(PR), and Infrastructure Readiness (IR) using 15 items per dimension on a five-point scale, with higher scores indicating greater readiness (Panda & Mishra, 2007). By ensuring that the questionnaire was designed to fully reflect the research objectives the tool's content validity was confirmed (Babbie & Mouton, 2007), with revisions based on expert feedback to improve and ensure face validity by rectifying double barreled items. The final 43-item scale demonstrated high reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.89), with strong coefficients for each dimension (TR = 0.80, PR = 0.73, IR = 0.80)(Heale & Twycross, 2015). Targeting students in J&K's higher education institutions (HEIs), we used AISHE 2018-19 data to reach students of 236 HEIs. Data was collected online (Schillewaert & Meulemeester, 2005), maintaining confidentiality and informed consent. The final sample included 909 students, meeting sample size criteria (Gay et al., 2012).

Participant's profile

Students from higher education institutions of J & K constituted the sample of the study. The demographic profile of the sample indicates nearly equal representation of male and female students. Additionally, the sample is well-balanced between students from HEIs located in urban and rural areas (table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Students

Variable	Category	No. of Participants	%
Gender	Male	491	54.02
	Female	418	45.99
Stream	Science and Technology	167	18.38
	Social Science	158	17.39
	Arts & Humanities	495	54.46
	Others	89	9.8
Location of the Institution (LoI)	Urban	438	48.19
	Rural	471	51.82
Type of Institution (ToI)	State University	617	67.88
	Central University	292	32.13
Total = 909			

Data Analysis

SPSS Version 26 was used for data analysis. ELR was studied using descriptive statistics. In drawing inferences, non-parametric tests were applied as the data was not normal. Post hoc analysis of significant results was conducted using the Games-Howell test, with effect size calculated and interpreted for significant findings.

Results

ELR of HEI students

After removing 115 outliers the data was observed to be normal distributed and hence the analysis was carried out on a sample of 794. Table 2 depicts readiness of students for e-learning is on higher side.

Table 2: Details of Students ELR

Readiness Dimension	N*	Mean (M)	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
TR	15	54.99	6.42	-0.23	0.18
PR	14	52.26	5.99	-0.25	1.14
IR	14	48.98	8.02	-0.92	1.40
ELR	43	156.25	15.98	-0.19	-0.27

*Items in each dimension

The average ELR score for students is 156.25, with a standard deviation of 15.98, indicating minimal variation in their ELR. Dimension wise mean scores reveal that students scored highest in terms of their TR followed by their PR and IR. The standard deviation scores further show that students are not much deviated in terms of their dimension wise readiness. In terms of students' ELR levels, about 17% fall into the low readiness category, 66% are classified as moderate, and 17% as high. Due to the uneven distribution of students among these levels and the lack of homogeneity in variance, the Welch test was employed to evaluate the equality of means across the three groups (Field, 2013). The results indicated a significant difference in ELR mean scores among students in the low, moderate, and high readiness categories (Welch (2, 293) = 2277.60, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that this difference is statistically significant. Additionally, the Games-Howell post hoc test confirmed these differences in mean scores among all three groups ($p < 0.05$).

Most and least aspects of readiness

A higher mean score on positive items indicated strong agreement with the statements, whereas on negative items, it reflected strong disagreement (Panda & Mishra, 2007). Figure 1a illustrates that the mean scores for positive statements related to the technological

dimension ranged from 3.67 to 4.28. This suggests that while students demonstrated some level of readiness, none of the statements scored above 4.28, indicating a moderate rather than strong technological preparedness for e-learning. On the other hand, the mean scores for negatively worded statements were relatively low, ranging from 2.39 to 2.64. These scores revealed specific areas where students lacked readiness, such as sharing files in Google Classroom (T14), downloading necessary software for e-learning (T3), and troubleshooting or reporting technical issues on e-learning platforms (T10, T5). However, students showed higher levels of readiness in several aspects: managing online meetings (T11), uploading and downloading files on cloud services (T13), installing software needed for e-learning (T4), multitasking (T2), accessing and retrieving data from online databases (T9), and addressing issues when accessing the internet (T6). Additionally, they expressed confidence in basic computer functions and peripherals (T1), using Learning Management Systems (LMS) (T12), participating in online courses (T15), utilizing asynchronous tools (T7), and learning new skills required for e-learning (T8).

Figure 1b illustrates that the mean scores for positive statements related to PR ranged from 3.92 to 4.16, with none exceeding 4.17. This indicates a moderate level of PR among students, suggesting room for improvement in this area. Lower mean scores, ranging from 2.52 to 2.7 for negative statements, reveal that students perceive e-learning as less effective (P7), find it uncomfortable to use (P6), and are hesitant due to fear of making mistakes (P9). Conversely, a mean score of 3.8 on the negative item P2 reflects disagreement with the notion that e-learning would entirely replace other teaching and learning methods. Students recognize that e-learning provides benefits, such as learning at their own pace and convenience (P12), saving time (P8), and enhancing conceptual understanding (P4). They feel motivated to learn (P5), believe e-learning can improve their performance (P10), and prefer using it as an assisted learning tool (P3). Additionally, students acknowledge that various e-learning facilities like e-lectures, e-notes, virtual labs, digital libraries etc have become a reality of higher education (P13). They actively use online discussions to resolve doubts (P11) and feel confident navigating e-learning platforms (P1), even managing to stay on task despite online distractions (P14).

Figure 1: Dimension wise aspects of high and low readiness

Figure 1c reveals that mean scores for positive statements related to IR range from 3.60 to 3.93, with none exceeding 3.93. This indicates that significant improvements are still needed in terms of infrastructure to fully support e-learning. Low mean scores for negative statements, between 2.39 and 2.51, highlight concerns among students, such as inadequate equipment at their institutions to support e-learning initiatives (I6) and unsatisfactory unlimited internet access (I3). Additionally, although libraries are automated (I14), remote access to library resources is reported as insufficient (I11). On a positive note, students acknowledge that their institutions maintain up-to-date website and provide campus-wide Wi-Fi (I9), alongside generally reliable internet access (I2). However, they note limited internet availability outside of class hours (I8). Students also agree that computer labs are equipped with an adequate number of well-maintained computers (I7, I4). They recognize that their institutions have the necessary infrastructure to support e-learning (I1) and have technical support teams available to address e-learning issues (I10), although the scores for these items suggest room for further enhancement.

Correlation among dimensions of ELR

ELR is a multidimensional construct, with studies identifying key dimensions for improvement. Gay (2016) focused on technical, lifestyle, and pedagogical readiness, while

Zine et al. (2023) examined awareness, desire, knowledge, ability, and reinforcement. Al-Rikabi and Montazer (2024) categorized ELR into infrastructure, human, and organizational components. Our study also found significant correlations among all dimensions of ELR at 0.01 level of significance. Specifically, the pairwise correlation coefficients between students' overall ELR and TR, PR, and IR were 0.815, 0.754, and 0.777, respectively, indicating strong and meaningful relationships, as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Correlation among dimensions of ELR

Demographic characteristics and ELR

Variation in ELR across Sex

Numerous studies have investigated the impact of gender on technology integration and attitudes toward technology (Basargekar and Singhavi, 2017; Buaneng-Andoh, 2012; Rasouli et al., 2016). However, a definitive conclusion regarding the role of gender in this context has yet to be established. Therefore, this study also considers gender as a variable. Gender is operationalized as sex in this study. The K-S test indicated that ELR scores of female ($D(360) = 0.062$, $p < 0.05$) and male ($D(434) = 0.086$, $p < 0.05$) students were not-normal. Hence, the Independent Samples Mann-Whitney U Test (U Test) was utilized. Figure 3 displays the dimension-wise and overall ELR mean rank scores of male and female students.

Figure 3: Dimension wise and overall ELR mean rank scores of Male and Female students

Table 3 depicts that there was a significant but small difference between male and female students in terms of TR ($U = 66091.5$, $z = -3.744$, $p < 0.05$, $r = -0.132$). However, there was no such difference in terms of PR ($U = 77319.5$, $z = -.249$, $p > 0.05$) and IR ($U = 73378.5$, $z = -1.476$, $p > 0.05$). Similarly, there was no significant difference in terms of overall ELR ($U = 75139.0$, $z = -.927$, $p > 0.05$).

Table 3: Influence of Sex on Dimensions and overall ELR of students

Dimension	Gender (U)		Z	Sig	Effect size	Remarks
	Male (n= 434)	Female (n=360)				
TR		66091.5	-3.74	.00*	-0.13	Small
PR		77319.5	-0.24	0.80		
IR		73378.5	-1.47	0.14		
Overall ELR		75139	-0.92	0.35		

*Significant

It suggests that male demonstrate higher TR than female. However, there was no significant difference between them in terms of PR, IR or overall ELR.

Variation in ELR across LoI

The K-S test indicated that the ELR scores of students from institutions in urban and rural areas were not-normal ($D(365) = 0.08$, $p < 0.05$; $D(429) = 0.05$, $p < 0.05$). Figure 4 displays the dimension-wise and overall ELR mean rank scores of students studying in institutions in urban and rural areas.

Figure 4: Dimension wise and overall ELR mean rank scores of students from institutions in Urban and Rural areas

The results of U test presented in Table 4 indicate that there were no significant differences TR, PR, IR and overall ELR of students from urban and rural institutions.

Table 4: Influence of LoI on Dimensions and overall ELR of students

Dimension	Location of Institution (U)		Z	Sig
	Urban (n= 365)	Rural (n=429)		
TR		77258.5	-0.32	0.74
PR		76997.5	-0.40	0.68
IR		75613.5	-0.83	0.40
Overall ELR		77850	-0.13	0.89

Variation in ELR across ToI

The K-S test indicated that the ELR scores of students of Central and State institutions were significantly not-normal ($D(231) = 0.06, p < 0.05$; $D(563) = 0.08, p < 0.05$, respectively).

Figure 5 displays the dimension-wise and overall ELR mean rank scores of students from Central and State institutions.

Figure 5: Dimension wise and overall ELR mean rank scores of students from Central and State institutions

Results of U test shown in table 5 indicate that TR, PR, IR and overall ELR of students from Central and State institutions did not differ significantly and are almost same.

Table 5: Influence of ToI on Dimensions and overall ELR of students

Dimension	Type of Institution (U)		Z	Sig
	Central (n= 231)	State (n=563)		
TR		63813.5	-0.41	0.77
PR		64248	-0.26	0.69
IR		63689.5	-0.45	0.79
Overall ELR		64172.5	-0.29	0.64

Variation in ELR across Academic Stream

The K-S test revealed that the ELR of students from Science and Technology ($D(154) = 0.08, p < 0.05$) and Arts and Humanities ($D(466) = 0.06, p < 0.05$) and Other Streams ($D(81) = 0.12, p < 0.05$) were significantly not-normal and hence “Independent Samples Kruskal Wallis test” was applied to study the influence of academic stream on ELR and its dimensions. The figure6 shows stream wise dimension and overall ELR mean rank scores of students.

Figure 6: Dimension wise and overall ELR mean rank scores of students from various streams

There is significant difference in the TR, IR and ELR of students from various academic streams ($H(3) = 20.50, p < 0.05$; $H(3) = 11.22, p < 0.05$; $H(3) = 13.01, p < 0.05$) (table 6). However, the stream of the students did not have any influence on their PR. Pair-wise

comparison for overall ELR with Bonferroni correction for multiple tests revealed that the interaction between Arts & Humanities-Science and Technology; Arts & Humanities-Social Science, Others-Social Science were significant at 0.05 level of significance and in remaining cases the interaction was not significant (table 7).The aspects of ELR in which differences were observed among students of various streams is shown in figure 7.

Table 6: Influence of Academic Stream on Dimensions and overall ELR of students

Dimension	Discipline (H) (df =3)				Sig
	Science & Technology (n= 154)	Social Sciences (n=93)	Arts & Humanities (n = 466)	Others (n = 81)	
TR		20.50			0.00*
PR		6.68			0.08
IR		11.22			0.01*
Overall ELR		13.01			0.00*

Table 7 Pairwise Comparisons of Academic Stream on ELR

Sample 1-Sample 2	Test Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Test Statistic	Sig.
<u>Arts & Humanities-Others</u>	<u>-13.89</u>	<u>27.6</u>	<u>-0.50</u>	<u>0.61</u>
<u>Arts & Humanities-Science and Technology</u>	<u>52.95</u>	<u>21.31</u>	<u>2.48</u>	<u>0.01</u>
<u>Arts & Humanities-Social Science</u>	<u>79.42</u>	<u>26.03</u>	<u>3.05</u>	<u>0.00</u>
<u>Others-Science and Technology</u>	<u>39.05</u>	<u>31.46</u>	<u>1.24</u>	<u>0.21</u>
<u>Others-Social Science</u>	<u>65.52</u>	<u>34.84</u>	<u>1.88</u>	<u>0.06</u>
<u>Science and Technology-Social Science</u>	<u>-26.47</u>	<u>30.10</u>	<u>-0.87</u>	<u>0.37</u>

Figure 7: Academic Stream wise aspects of significant difference in ELR

Discussion

This research investigated e-learning readiness (ELR) among higher education students in Jammu and Kashmir, India, focusing on their preparedness across different dimensions, correlations among these dimensions, and the influence of demographics on ELR. Students from both state and central institutions were categorized into three ELR levels: Low, Moderate, and High. Using the Welch test, we found significant differences in ELR scores across these groups. The study's findings reveal a pressing need to improve students' readiness for e-learning, with institutions encouraged to target specific areas where students may lack preparation. While most participants showed moderate ELR, studies elsewhere, like Sevim-Cirak et al. (2023), report generally high ELR among college students, although specific areas such as motivation score lower. Research by Korkmaz and Toraman (2021) also highlights that medical students with strong technical skills tend to show higher ELR, particularly in online engagement and motivation. Similarly, Mokhtar et al. (2020) found that attitude and knowledge significantly influenced ELR among university students, while Kalkan (2020) noted that internet self-efficacy was a major strength, with motivation often a weaker area. Widyanti et al. (2020) also reported that ELR of students in an Indonesian university is high and most students have technical readiness but have low readiness in terms of learning behaviour towards e-learning. Interestingly, our findings aligned with other studies that technical readiness (TR) is often high, yet psychological readiness (PR) lags. This

is echoed by Elçiçek and Erdemci (2021), who observed that while students possess strong 21st-century competencies, their overall ELR tends to be moderate. Together, these studies indicate that beyond technical skills, attitudes and motivation are essential components of readiness for e-learning.

The findings also show that students are generally well-prepared in areas such as managing online meetings, using cloud services, and basic computer functions. They exhibit strong e-learning skills, like file handling and using Learning Management Systems (LMS), and appreciate the flexibility of e-learning to improve performance. While they value e-learning's ability to let them learn at their own pace, they do not believe it will fully replace traditional methods. Students' digital abilities significantly influence their attitudes toward ICT, with e-learning users being more intrinsically motivated than traditional learners (Rodrigues et al., 2019). However, challenges persist, especially with file-sharing and troubleshooting on platforms like Google Classroom. Despite recognizing that their institutions provide reliable infrastructure, including up-to-date websites and well-equipped computer labs, students express concerns about inadequate equipment and limited internet access outside class hours. Reyes et al. (2021) found that students are confident in their basic tech skills but lack preparedness in managing online learning platforms and exercising learner control. Similarly, Wagiran et al. (2022) emphasized that enhancing students' online learning readiness requires improvements in technological skills, equipment access, user satisfaction, and motivation. Furthermore, barriers like slow internet speeds and unfamiliarity with e-learning platforms hinder effective ELR (Octaberlina & Muslimin, 2020). Remote access to library resources remains underexplored but could greatly improve the flexibility and effectiveness of online education. Overall, there is a clear need for improved digital skills and infrastructure to optimize ELR.

The study further found that gender had no significant impact on students' e-learning readiness (ELR), with both male and female students exhibiting similar readiness levels. This aligns with previous research suggesting that the gender gap in technology access has decreased post-COVID, providing equal e-learning opportunities (Ramírez-Correa et al., 2015). Mokhtar et al. (2020) and Yawson and Yamoah (2020) also found minimal gender differences in attitudes toward e-learning. However, some studies report gender-related variations in specific areas. Elçiçek and Erdemci (2021) found female students had higher 21st-century competencies, while Kabir et al. (2021) noted males were more e-learning ready. Martha et al. (2021) observed that females excelled in openness and organization,

while males were better at time management. Additionally, Abbas (2017) found that females showed greater intention to use e-learning. Zine et al. (2023) reported the presence of gender-related disparities in ELR. These mixed findings underscore the need to further explore gender's influence on e-learning readiness.

This study found no significant impact of institutional location on students' e-learning readiness (ELR). This contrasts with previous research by Das and Dansana (2022) and Elnakeeb et al. (2016) which suggested that urban students are more prepared for e-learning. Martha et al. (2021) also highlighted differences, with rural students excelling in idea generation and collaboration, while urban students were more skilled in engaging with online reviews. Despite these findings, our study indicates that other factors, rather than institutional location, likely influence ELR, regardless of whether students are from urban or rural areas.

The study also explored the influence of institution type on students' e-learning readiness (ELR). Surprisingly, results revealed no significant differences between students from central and state institutions, indicating that the type of institution did not affect their ELR. This aligns with previous studies by Kaushik and Agarwal (2021), Lucero et al. (2021), and Majid & Vijaya Lakshmi (2023), which also found no notable impact of institution type on ELR. Similarly, Kabir et al. (2021) reported no significant association between institution type and ELR scores among university students, further supporting these findings.

The study found that students in the Social Science stream demonstrated higher e-learning readiness (ELR) compared to their peers in Science and Technology, Arts & Humanities, and other streams. This was evident in various ELR aspects, including computer awareness, multitasking, software installation, and data retrieval from online resources. These findings align with research by Adams et al. (2018), Kalkan (2020), and Martha et al. (2021), who highlighted the influence of academic streams on ELR across factors like email communication, online discussions, basic computer skills, and time management.

Recommendations and Conclusion

This study assessed the e-learning readiness (ELR) of students in higher education institutions (HEIs) in Jammu and Kashmir using the "E-Learning Readiness of Students" scale, which focuses on three core dimensions. Conducted as a cross-sectional descriptive study, it occurred during a period of significant regional change, including the revocation of Article 370 in Jammu and Kashmir. Given the evolving educational landscape, replicating or

extending this study could provide valuable insights, particularly through longitudinal research that tracks how ELR evolves as digital education grows.

To enhance ELR, improving students' technical skills through targeted training on platform usage, troubleshooting, and file sharing in cloud is crucial to boosting digital confidence. Expanding campus Wi-Fi, investing in reliable internet access, creating equipment loan programs, and offering remote access to digital libraries can significantly improve learning flexibility and minimize disruptions. Encouraging collaborative online activities and fostering a supportive environment can motivate students while reducing their fear of making mistakes. Additionally, addressing psychological barriers through mental health resources and peer support networks can alleviate e-learning stress, increasing student comfort.

Given India's diverse higher education system, a national study led by bodies like the UGC or IGNOU could provide valuable insights for developing e-learning policy guidelines. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 highlights the importance of digital learning, making further research into ELR crucial for shaping the future of education in India. India needs indigenous models reflecting its unique educational context, similar to international ELR models (Aishammari & Adaileh, 2018; Al-Rikabi & Montazer, 2024; Wibowo & Laksitowening, 2015).

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